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Correlation Between Initial Platelet Count And Disease Severity In Dengue In Pediatric Population

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: To determine whether initial platelet count predicts the severity of dengue (DF vs DHF vs DSS).

Materials and Methods: After approval from the Ethical Committee of Holy Family Hospital, Islamabad, 124 patients meeting the selection criteria were enrolled after obtaining written informed consent. Demographic data were recorded, and patients were classified into three groups: DF, DHF, and DSS. Blood samples were collected via standard aseptic venipuncture into EDTA tubes and analyzed within two hours using a Sysmex automated hematology analyzer for complete blood count, including platelet count ($\times 10^9/L$). Abnormal results were verified manually by peripheral smear examination. Data were collected using a predesigned questionnaire and analyzed using SPSS Version 25 with strict quality control measures maintained throughout.

Results: The mean age was 8.55 ± 2.95 years. By group, the mean age was 8.54 ± 2.46 years in DHF, 8.63 ± 3.12 years in DF, and 7.20 ± 2.86 years in DSS. Males constituted 64.5% of DHF, 70.5% of DF, and 80% of DSS cases. IgG positivity was seen in 61.3% of DHF and 33.0% of DF cases, with none in DSS, while IgM positivity occurred in 71.0% of DHF, 69.3% of DF, and 40% of DSS cases. NS1 antigen was detected in 64.5% of DHF, 79.5% of DF, and all DSS cases. Mean hematocrit was 34.61 ± 5.89 in DHF, 34.27 ± 5.37 in DF, and 30.60 ± 6.65 in DSS. Mean TLC was 4551.61 ± 2263.16 , 4685.22 ± 7984.43 , and 4720.00 ± 3267.56 , respectively. Average hospital stay was 1.32 ± 0.79 days for DHF, 1.48 ± 0.85 days for DF, and 1.60 ± 0.89 days for DSS. Mean platelet counts were $71,516.12 \pm 31,100.77$ in DHF, $92,568.18 \pm 36,958.75$ in DF, and $78,000.00 \pm 36,789.94$ in DSS, with a statistically significant difference between groups ($p = 0.01$).

Conclusion: It was concluded that lower platelet counts in severe cases (DHF, DSS) suggest early thrombocytopenia as a potential marker for identifying high-risk patients. Combined with other parameters, it can aid early risk assessment, though further large-scale studies are needed for validation.

INTRODUCTION:

Dengue fever is a viral infection and represents a significant global health concern..(1) The illness manifests in varying degrees of severity, from mild dengue fever (DF) to dengue hemorrhagic fever (DHF) and, in severe cases, to the potentially fatal dengue shock syndrome (DSS).(2) Early assessment of disease severity is crucial to prevent complications and reduce mortality. Dengue continues to pose a major clinical and public health concern worldwide.(3) Over 2.5 billion people in tropical and subtropical regions risk the disease, with about 390 million cases yearly in nearly 125 countries..(4, 5) Young adults and children are the demographic most impacted. Aedes mosquitoes are the vector-borne vector of this infectious disease.(6, 7)

An important laboratory parameter in the diagnosis is the platelet count.(8) Thrombocytopenia is a common and characteristic laboratory finding in dengue and can be associated with an increased risk of bleeding and more severe disease.(9, 10) The initial platelet count on admission could therefore be a valuable predictor for assessing disease severity.

This study aims to assess the link between initial platelet count and disease severity to offer potential prognostic insights for managing dengue patients.

Objective: To determine whether initial platelet count predicts the severity of dengue (DF vs DHF vs DSS).

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study Design: Cross-sectional Retrospective study.

Study setting: Department of Pediatric Medicine Holy Family Hospital Rawalpindi

Duration of the study: Duration of the study was 6 month 1/6/24 to 30/12/24.

Sampling Technique: • Non-probability consecutive sampling was used for the recruitment of patients.

Inclusion Criteria:

Patients of age 1-12 years

Both genders (male and female)

Patients with confirmed diagnosis of dengue fever according to WHO criteria.

Patients who presented to the emergency room or hospital within 5 days of symptom onset

Exclusion Criteria:

Patients with pre-existing hematological diseases that affect platelet count (e.g., idiopathic thrombocytopenic purpura, leukemia)

Patients with chronic liver disease or other systemic diseases that can cause thrombocytopenia

Patients who have already received a platelet concentrate transfusion prior to hospital admission.

Pregnant women

Methods:

After the approval of ethical committee of Holy family hospital, Islamabad, patients fulfill the selection criteria were enrolled. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants. A total of 124 patients were enrolled in the study, and each underwent a thorough clinical examination. All demographic information was recorded, and the enrolled patients were categorized into three groups: DF, DHF, and DSS. Group A consists of patients with DF, Group B consists of patients with DHF and Group C consists of Blood samples were collected using a standard venipuncture technique under aseptic conditions into EDTA tubes to prevent coagulation.

The collected samples were analyzed within two hours using an automated hematology analyzer (Sysmex). A CBC was performed, and the platelet count (expressed in $\times 10^9/L$) was recorded. In cases where the

automated results showed abnormalities, manual verification was conducted through peripheral blood smear examination by a trained laboratory technician or pathologist. Stringent quality control measures were maintained throughout the testing process to ensure accurate and reliable platelet count results. A predesign questionnaire were used to collect data. The collected data were entered and analyzed using the SPSS version 25.

RESULTS:

The mean age was 8.55 ± 2.95 years (Table 1). The mean age of patients was 8.54 ± 2.46 years in the DHF group, 8.63 ± 3.12 years in the DF group, and 7.20 ± 2.86 years in the DSS group. Males comprised 64.5% of DHF, 70.5% of DF, and 80% of DSS cases, while females accounted for 35.5%, 29.5%, and 20%, respectively. IgG positivity was observed in 61.3% of DHF and 33.0% of DF cases, with none in DSS, whereas IgM positivity was found in 71.0% of DHF, 69.3% of DF, and 40% of DSS cases. NS1 antigen was detected in 64.5% of DHF, 79.5% of DF, and all DSS cases. Mean hematocrit values were 34.61 ± 5.89 in DHF, 34.27 ± 5.37 in DF, and 30.60 ± 6.65 in DSS. Mean TLC values were 4551.61 ± 2263.16 , 4685.22 ± 7984.43 , and 4720.00 ± 3267.56 for DHF, DF, and DSS groups, respectively. Average hospital stay was 1.32 ± 0.79 days for DHF, 1.48 ± 0.85 days for DF, and 1.60 ± 0.89 days for DSS (Table 2). The mean platelet count was $71,516.12 \pm 31,100.77$ in the DHF group, $92,568.18 \pm 36,958.75$ in the DF group, and $78,000.00 \pm 36,789.94$ in the DSS group, with a statistically significant difference among the groups ($p = 0.01$) (Table 3).

Table 1: Mean Age of all enrolled patients (n=124)

Variables	
Age (Years)	8.55 ± 2.95

Fig 1: Frequency of patients on the basis of gender

Table 2: Comparison of Demographic, Serological, and Hematological Parameters Among Patients with Dengue Fever (DF), Dengue Hemorrhagic Fever (DHF), and Dengue Shock Syndrome (DSS) (n=124)

Variables	Groups		
	DHF	DF	DSS
Age	8.54±2.46	8.63±3.12	7.20±2.86
Gender			
Male	20(64.5%)	62(70.5%)	4(80.0%)
Female	11(35.5%)	26(29.5%)	1(20.0%)
IGG			
Yes	19(61.3%)	29(33.0%)	0(00.0%)
No	12(38.7%)	59(67.0%)	5(100.0%)
IGM			
Yes	22(71.0%)	61(69.3%)	2(40.0%)
No	9(29.0%)	27(30.7%)	3(60.0%)
NS1			
Yes	20(64.5%)	70(79.5%)	5(100.0%)
No	11(35.5%)	18(20.5%)	0(00.0%)
HCT	34.61±5.89	34.27±5.37	30.60±6.65
TLC	4551.61±263.16	4685.22±7984.43	4720.00±3267.56
Stay in Hospital (Days)	1.32±0.79	1.48±0.85	1.60±0.89

Table 3: Comparison of Mean Platelet Count Among Patients with Dengue Fever (DF), Dengue Hemorrhagic Fever (DHF), and Dengue Shock Syndrome (DSS) (n=124)

Variables	Groups			p-value
	DHF	DF	DSS	
Platelets	71516.12 ± 31100.77	92568.18 ± 36958.75	78000.0 ± 36789.94	0.01

Discussion:

The present study seeks to determine whether initial platelet count predicts the severity of dengue (DF vs DHF vs DSS).

The finding of the present study show that the mean platelet count varied significantly between the groups studied and could therefore be a potential indicator of disease severity. Participants with DHF and DSS had, on average, lower platelet counts than patients with classic DF, supporting the hypothesis that more pronounced thrombocytopenia is associated with more severe disease manifestation. Sure — here’s a refined rephrasing of your sentence: In dengue-endemic regions, a combination of low platelet count, reduced MPV and plateletcrit PCT, together with elevated PDW, may serve as potential markers for identifying dengue infection as well as predicting its severity.(5) A study by Chiranth S.B. et al.(5) found

that platelet indices are reduced in dengue infection. In particular, a reduced platelet count and a PCT are directly related to disease severity. These parameters can therefore serve as useful markers for both diagnosis and assessment of disease progression. A study by Bashir et al.(11) that dengue fever patients exhibited reduced MPV and platelet counts, along with increased PDW values. Navya et al.(12) showed that platelet count can be used as a predictor of dengue fever and noted that a low MPV together with a high PDW is highly sensitive for identifying the disease. Hardeva et al.(13) demonstrated a significant association between platelet count and disease severity. A low platelet count, reduced MPV and PCT, and an increased PDW collectively demonstrate considerable sensitivity and specificity for dengue fever and can serve as markers for predicting disease progression. Similar results were also reported by Krishnamurthy et al.(14) and Kumar et al. (15).

The observed significant correlation between low initial platelet count and higher disease severity can be explained pathophysiologically by increased destruction and consumption of platelets as part of the immune response, as well as by a possible impairment of megakaryopoiesis in the bone marrow. Previous studies have also shown that a rapid decline in platelet count can be a prognostic marker for the transition from a mild to a severe course of the disease. The primary reason for thrombocytopenia in the acute phase of dengue fever is suppression of the bone marrow.(16) Marrow suppression is suggested as the underlying mechanism when a low mean platelet volume (MPV) is linked to decreased platelet numbers.(17) A growing MPV, on the other hand, suggests greater peripheral platelet breakdown and may indicate the need for platelet transfusion when chronic thrombocytopenia is present. Conversely, the start of recovery is more likely to be indicated by an increase in MPV along with a constant platelet count.(18)

Interestingly, although the average platelet count in DSS patients was lower than in DF patients, it was not always lower than in DHF patients. This may indicate that, in addition to thrombocytopenia, other factors, such as plasma leak, cytokine storm, and individual immune response, play a crucial role in the severity.

Another relevant aspect is that platelet counts alone are not sufficient to predict the clinical course, but in combination with other laboratory parameters such as hematocrit, white blood cell count, and serological markers (IgM, IgG, NS1 antigen), they can be a useful tool for risk management.

The results of this study suggest that determining the initial platelet count at the initial presentation of a dengue patient should be considered as a simple, cost-effective, and rapid marker for assessing the risk of severe disease. However, prospective, multicenter studies with larger sample sizes are needed to validate the diagnostic and prognostic value of this parameter.

Conclusion: It was concluded that patients with severe forms, such as DHF and DSS, tended to present with lower platelet counts compared to those with DF, indicating that early thrombocytopenia may serve as a useful clinical marker for identifying individuals at risk of severe disease progression. While platelet count alone cannot determine the complete clinical outcome, its use in conjunction with other laboratory and clinical parameters may improve early risk stratification and guide timely intervention. Larger prospective studies are needed to confirm these findings and to define standardized cut-off values for clinical use.

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